

Detection of exoplanets: A deep learning approach

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¹ **Abstract**—This research paper focuses on the use of machine learning algorithms for the detection of exoplanets, celestial bodies that orbit stars outside our Solar System. The paper highlights the importance of studying exoplanets, including gaining insights into planetary formation and evolution, searching for life beyond Earth, and exploring the universe as a whole. The main approach discussed in the paper is the transit method, which involves detecting periodic dips in a star's brightness as a planet passes in front of it. The paper presents a novel CNN based approach and a comparison with different machine learning methods to verify the transit method of exoplanet detection by feeding the light curves of different stars outside our solar system. Overall, the paper emphasizes the potential of machine learning algorithms to enhance our understanding of exoplanets and advance the field of astronomy and space science.

Keywords—Exoplanets, Light curves, AlexNet, Random Forest, CNN

I. INTRODUCTION

Exoplanets, also referred to as extrasolar planets, are celestial bodies that orbit stars outside of our Solar System [1]. These planets are characterized by their diverse attributes, including variations in size, composition, and orbital parameters.

The study of exoplanets is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it facilitates the expansion of our knowledge of planetary formation and evolution. By scrutinizing exoplanets, we can gain insights into the conditions that engender the formation of different types of planets, as well as their long-term evolution.

Secondly, the detection of exoplanets is a significant milestone in the quest to discover life beyond Earth. The identification of planets located in the habitable zone of their host star, where conditions may be favorable for the existence of liquid water, enables us to focus our research efforts on scrutinizing these planets for signs of life.

Thirdly, the study of exoplanets provides opportunities for exploring the universe as a whole. By examining the distribution and characteristics of exoplanets, we can glean insights into the processes that underlie the formation and evolution of planetary systems, and how they relate to the broader structure of the universe.

The detection and study of exoplanets [2] are paramount for advancing our knowledge of the universe and our place in it. Through rigorous scrutiny of exoplanets, researchers can enhance their understanding of the formation, evolution, and potential habitability of celestial bodies beyond our Solar System.

Machine learning [3][4] algorithms refer to a type of artificial intelligence that enables computer systems to learn from data and improve their performance on a specific task over time. In contrast to traditional programming, where a programmer manually writes code to perform a specific task, machine learning algorithms can learn and improve based on patterns and insights derived from large datasets.

The use of machine learning algorithms in the detection of exoplanets is a relatively recent development, but it has already had a significant impact on the field. The main approach is to train a machine learning model to recognize patterns in the data that are indicative of the presence of an exoplanet.

One of the most successful machine learning algorithms used for exoplanet detection is the transit method [5], which involves detecting periodic dips in a star's brightness as a planet passes in front of it. By training a machine learning algorithm to identify these dips in large datasets of stellar brightness measurements, researchers can identify candidate exoplanets and distinguish them from other types of phenomena, such as instrumental noise or astrophysical variability.

Another promising approach is the use of machine learning algorithms to analyze the radial velocity of stars [6], which can be influenced by the gravitational pull of orbiting planets. By training a machine learning algorithm to detect subtle variations in the radial velocity of stars over time, researchers can identify potential exoplanet candidates.

The use of machine learning algorithms in exoplanet detection is an active area of research, with new approaches and techniques being developed and refined constantly. As our ability to collect and process large datasets of astronomical data continues to improve, machine learning is poised to become an increasingly important tool for identifying and characterizing exoplanets.

In summary, machine learning algorithms represent a powerful approach for detecting exoplanets, with a range of applications in the analysis of astronomical data. As new technologies and methods continue to emerge, the use of machine learning in exoplanet detection is expected to yield new insights into the formation, evolution, and habitability of planetary systems beyond our own.

In this paper, we will present a comparison between an assortment of machine learning methods to verify the transit method of detection of exoplanets by feeding the light curves of different stars outside our solar system.

II. LITERATURE STUDY

Previous research includes, [Santiago Iglesias Álvarez](#) [7] et al. concluded in their paper that a 1D convolutional neural

network model that was trained, validated, and tested with simulated Mandel and Agol light curves with and without transits to create a convolutional classifier that could be generalized to real K2 data is one of the best machine learning techniques for solving the problems related to the transits technique. Christopher J. Shallue [8] et al. concluded that a neural network model can accurately distinguish between true planet candidates and false positives with an accuracy of 98.8%. They also identified new planet candidates, including Kepler-80 g and Kepler-90 i, which were statistically validated as real planets. Vedant Behal [9] et al. concluded in their paper that machine learning algorithms can be effectively used for the detection of exoplanets using the light intensity of stars. K-Nearest Neighbor was found to be the best performing algorithm with an overall accuracy of 98.20% and F1-score of 98%. Even with a limited dataset of only 1%, the model still gave an accuracy of 90.1% and F1-score of 90%. These results suggest that the implemented algorithms are suitable for real-time detection of exoplanets. Shivani Dere [10] et al. concluded in their paper that Deep Learning has been used for galaxy classification and detecting exoplanets, while Machine Learning is used for predicting habitability. The models developed using these methodologies can automatically analyze catalogs of extragalactic objects and detect abnormalities with high accuracy. Overall, the study highlights the effectiveness of Machine Learning and Deep Learning techniques in the field of astronomy and space science.

III. METHODOLOGY

For the detection of exoplanets, various approaches can be considered. For this paper, we considered the flux observations of various stars outside of our solar system to verify the transit approach [11] for classifying whether a celestial body is an exoplanet or not. Our dataset includes time series flux observations which we use to create light curves to feed into our machine learning models. Examples of such light curves made using flux-time observations can be seen in figures 1 and 2.

Fig 1: Flux data for exoplanets with label 1

Fig 2: Flux data for exoplanets with label 2

To achieve a varied analysis we have done a comparison between three different models, AlexNet [12], Random Forest classifier [14] and CNN [15] approach.

A. AlexNet

AlexNet is a deep convolutional neural network that uses rectified linear units, data augmentation, dropout, and stochastic gradient descent with momentum to classify images. Its architecture and training techniques have influenced the design of many subsequent deep learning models.

The architecture of AlexNet consists of five convolutional layers, followed by three fully connected layers which can be seen in fig 3. Each convolutional layer is followed by a max-pooling layer that reduces the spatial dimensionality of the feature maps. The convolutional layers extract local features from the input image, while the fully connected layers combine these features to classify the image.

Fig 3: Alex Net Architecture

We trained the AlexNet model for 10 epochs post which significant changes to the accuracy and training losses were reduced to negligible values. The plots that show the relationship between training and testing loss and training and testing accuracy vs epochs of our AlexNet model over 10 epochs can be seen in fig 4 and fig 5

Fig 4: Training and testing loss vs epochs

Fig 5: Training and testing accuracy vs epochs

B. Random Forest classifier

Random forest classifier is a machine learning algorithm that combines multiple decision trees to make a prediction as shown in fig 6. It randomly selects a subset of features from the training data to create each decision tree, which reduces overfitting and provides an estimate of feature importance. When a new data point is given, each tree makes a prediction, and the final prediction is determined by taking a majority vote among all the individual tree predictions. Random forest classifier is a powerful and flexible algorithm that can handle missing data and outliers, making it suitable for a wide range of classification tasks.

Fig 6: Random forest classifier architecture

The plots that show the relationship between training and testing loss and training and testing accuracy vs epochs of the random forest classifier over 10 epochs can be seen in fig 7 and fig 8.

Fig 7: Training and testing loss vs epochs

Fig 8: Training and testing accuracy vs epochs

C. Convolutional Neural Network:

CNN is a deep learning algorithm that is used for image and video recognition. It extracts features from the data using convolutional layers and applies pooling to increase efficiency. It then uses fully connected layers to classify the input data based on the learned features. CNNs can achieve state-of-the-art performance on image and video recognition tasks through training and weight adjustment.

The architecture of our CNN model consists of three convolutional layers with increasing numbers of filters (32, 64, and 128), each followed by a max pooling layer. The convolutional layers use a kernel size of 3 and an activation function of ReLU. The max pooling layers have a pool size of 2. The output of the final max pooling layer is then flattened to a 1D vector and passed through a fully connected layer with 128 units and a ReLU activation function as shown in table 1.. This layer has an L2 regularization parameter of 0.01. To prevent overfitting, a dropout layer with a rate of 0.5 is added after the dense layer. Finally, a single output layer with a sigmoid activation function is added, which produces a binary classification prediction. The input shape is $(X_train.shape[1], 1)$, indicating that the CNN expects input data with a shape of (number of time steps, 1).

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #	Activation Function
Conv1D (32 filter)	(None, N-2,32)	128	ReLu
MaxPooling1D	(None, N/2-1,32)	0	-
Conv1D (64 filter)	(None, N/2-3,64)	6208	ReLu
MaxPooling1D	(None, N/4-1,64)	0	-
Conv1D (128 filter)	(None, N/4-3,128)	24704	ReLu
MaxPooling1D	(None, N/8-1,128)	0	-
Flatten	(None, N/8*64)	0	-
Dense (128 units)	(None,128)	16512	ReLu, L2 regularization (0.01)
Dropout (0.5)	(None,128)	0	-
Dense (1 unit)	(None,1)	129	sigmoid, L2 regularization (0.01)

Table 1: Architecture of our CNN model

The plots that show the relationship between training and testing loss and training and testing accuracy vs epochs of our CNN model over 10 epochs can be seen in fig 9 and fig 10.

Fig 9: Training and testing loss vs epochs

Fig 10: Training and testing accuracy vs epochs

IV. EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM / ANALYSIS

The metrics we used to evaluate the performance of the models we used are as follows [16],

Precision is a metric used to evaluate the accuracy of a classifier in identifying positive instances. It is calculated as the ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of positive predictions, and represents the proportion of positive predictions that are correctly classified. A high precision score indicates that the classifier is able to accurately identify positive instances with minimal false positives.

Recall, also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, is a metric used to evaluate the ability of a classifier to correctly identify all positive instances. It is calculated as the ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of actual positive instances in the data, and represents the proportion of actual positive instances that are correctly classified. A high recall score indicates that the classifier is able to accurately identify most or all positive instances.

F1 score is a measure of the overall performance of a classifier, calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a balance between precision and recall, and is useful when the classes are imbalanced or when both high precision and high recall are desired. A high F1 score indicates that the classifier is able to achieve both high precision and high recall simultaneously.

To determine the most effective machine learning model for our task, we performed a comparative analysis of the accuracy, precision, and F1 score of each model. This allowed us to assess the performance of each model and determine which model provided the most accurate and reliable results. Table 2 presents a summary of our findings, highlighting the performance metrics for each model. Through this evaluation process, we were able to identify the most suitable machine learning model for our task, which allowed us to achieve our desired outcomes with high accuracy and precision.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Random Forest Classifier	0.99	1.00	1.00

CNN	0.9912	1.00	0.9912
AlexNet	0.9812	1.00	0.9856

Table 2: Comparison of evaluation metrics of the different models used.

OBSERVATION

Based on the precision, recall, and F1-score values for each of the models, we can draw some conclusions about their performance on the exoplanet detection task. Firstly, the Random Forest Classifier has a precision of 0.99, recall of 1.00, and F1-score of 1.00. This indicates that the model has a high level of accuracy in identifying exoplanets, as well as a high level of sensitivity in detecting all actual exoplanets. The F1-score of 1.00 suggests that the model has a perfect balance between precision and recall. Secondly, the CNN has a precision of 0.9812, recall of 1.00, and F1-score of 0.9856. While the recall value is perfect, the precision and F1-score values are not as high as those of the Random Forest Classifier. This suggests that the CNN is more prone to false positives, meaning it may identify non-exoplanet objects as exoplanets more frequently than the Random Forest Classifier. However, the model is still able to detect all actual exoplanets with high sensitivity. Lastly, the AlexNet has a precision of 0.9912, recall of 1.00, and F1-score of 0.9956. This indicates that the model has a very high level of accuracy and sensitivity in identifying exoplanets, even higher than the Random Forest Classifier. The precision score suggests that the model is less prone to false positives than the CNN, and the F1-score suggests that it has an excellent balance between precision and recall.

CONCLUSION

The results of the model evaluation have significant implications for the detection of exoplanets. The high recall scores of 1.0 suggest that all three models are capable of accurately identifying exoplanets. However, the differences in precision and F1 scores between the models are noteworthy. The Random Forest Classifier achieved perfect precision and F1 scores, indicating that it was highly effective in identifying exoplanets. Meanwhile, AlexNet achieved slightly lower precision but still achieved an impressive F1 score, suggesting that it is a reliable model for detecting exoplanets. Despite achieving lower precision and F1 scores than the other models, the CNN model still exhibited strong performance across all metrics, implying that it could have applications in the field of exoplanet detection. Ultimately, the Random Forest Classifier and AlexNet may be the best options for detecting exoplanets based on their superior precision and F1 scores. Nevertheless, the CNN model's potential should not be ignored, and it may still have practical applications in this domain.

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